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Hemp Club

Competent and Connected
Clusters Unfold the Hemp
Industry Potential for the
European Bioeconomy

European Cluster Excellence Programme with ClusterXchange scheme connecting ecosystem and cities
COS-CLUSTER-2020-3-03

Grant Agreement No: 101037874

CALL FOR TRAINING TENDER DELIVERABLE 1.2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the development and the structure of the **Call for training tender** aimed at recruiting experts for cluster management capacity and skills building to develop a training programme for 14 cluster managers (2 from each cluster).

Based on the results of the joint survey carried out in WP1, WP2 and WP3, this call for training ensures that the expectations and needs of all partners are met in a training programme of 8 different modules for a total of 70 hours of training. The topics selected for the training are:

- Digital and analytical skills
- PM2 methodology
- Lean management
- Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies, etc
- EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization
- Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration
- Service orientation as a strategic marketing tool
- People management

The call also defines the duties and responsibilities of the trainers as well as the required skills and qualifications, thus ensuring the high quality of the training programme that the cluster managers will attend. Finally, the call defines the terms of the contract, focusing on reporting and payment and providing a clear and transparent framework for the evaluation of the proposal.

The call opened on the 31st of August 2022, being published on the project website, social media and ECCP, and will close on the 30th of September 2022.

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1. INTRODUCTION: AIMS AND SCOPE

This report describes the development and the structure of the Call for training tender: “*Experts recruitment for cluster management capacity and skills building*” as part of **Task 1.2 - Training actions for cluster managers** within the HempClub project. The general aim of this task is to design a training, mentoring and coaching programme from partners’ inputs to meet general expectations and requirements. As a starting point of this task, a tender for external suppliers (trainers) shall be designed, launched and publicly advertised.

In this context, the call for training tender (Annex 1) aims to recruit experts for cluster management capacity and skills building to develop a training programme for 14 cluster managers (2 from each cluster). The **specific objectives of the call** are:

- To recruit experts with an adequate professional background and specific experience, thus ensuring the high quality of training;
- To provide clear information on the duties and responsibilities of trainers;
- To meet general expectations and requirements from all seven project partners;
- To set a transparent framework for the evaluation of the proposals;
- To clearly define the terms for reporting and payment.

The training programme is based on 8 modules, for a total of 70 hours of training. The content of the training is based on the strategical and specific needs of the 7 clusters as identified in task 1.1 of the HempClub project (see the methodology paragraph for further details on the selection of training modules).

The specific objectives of the training as well as detailed information on duties and responsibilities, required qualifications, timeframe, location, reporting payment, instruction on how to apply and how applications are evaluated are described in details in Annex 1 – Call for training tender.

2. METHODOLOGY: SELECTION OF TRAINING MODULES

The 8 modules of the training programme were selected in order to respond to the specific needs of all the project partners. As part of the performance assessment of cluster carried out in T1.1, training needs were also evaluated for each partner.

The self-assessment survey template prepared jointly by PRODUTECH, LGCA, SPRING and CZECHEMP is divided in 5 sections:

- SECTION A – The cluster (Overview, Strategy, Structuring projects, Governance and Challenges)
- SECTION B – Provided services (General and Bio-economy related)
- SECTION C – Framework (General, S3 and Bioeconomy, Green Deal and Recovery and Resilience)
- SECTION D – Training needs
- SECTION E – Hemp focus

Section D contains specific questions to evaluate training needs. Partners were asked to: “given a specific sentence on training needs, defined your level of agreement by following a 7-point likert scale ranging from 1-Strongly Disagree to 7-Strongly agree (Table 1).

Strongly disagree	1
Disagree	2
More or less disagree	3
Undecided	4

More or less agree	5
Agree	6
Strongly agree	7

Table 1. 7-point likert scale

The evaluation of skills was divided into “Soft skills” (Table 2) and “Hard skills” (Table 3).

Our cluster managers needs to strenghten their soft skills on the following topics:	
Time management	
Communication skills	
People management	
Critical thinking	
Negotiation	
Service orientation	
Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration	
Public speaking for sales people	
Please, insert other cluster managers needs on soft skills	

Table 2. Soft skills

Our cluster managers needs to strenghten their hard skills on the following topics:	
Digital skills (software for project management)	
Digitalisation in processes	
Knowledge on value chain management and cluster development	
Organization of specific activities (e.g. working groups, round table) to involve cluster members in the decision making process	
Knowledge on EU funding opportunities	
Project management (PMG, lean management, Scrumble, ...)	
Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies,...	
EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization, with a focus on hemp	
Please, insert other cluster managers needs on hard skills	

Table 3. Hard skills

The answers from each partner were then collected. For each training needs, an average data was obtained as the average of the evaluation expressed by each partner.

After the definition of the most relevant training needs for the Partnership, the duration of each training modules was discussed and agreed between all partners. The budget for each training module was calculated according to the training hours.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Training modules selection

Based on the methodology described above, the following average results were obtained:

Our cluster managers needs to strenghten their soft skills on the following topics:	
Time management	3,71
Communication skills	3,57
People management	4,86
Critical thinking	3,71
Negotiation	3,57
Service orientation	5,57
Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration	5,42
Public speaking for sales people	3,14
Please, insert other cluster managers needs on soft skills	
No comments on this	

Our cluster managers needs to strenghten their hard skills on the following topics:	
Digital skills (software for project management)	5,14
Digitalisation in processes	3,86
Knowledge on value chain management and cluster development	4,29
Organization of specific activities (e.g. working groups, round table) to involve cluster members in the decision making process	4,43
Knowledge on EU funding opportunities	3,29
Project management (PMG, lean management, Scrumble, ...)	6,14
Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies,...	5,14
EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization, with a focus on hemp	5,14
Please, insert other cluster managers needs on hard skills	
No comments on this	

Table 4. Results of the training needs assessment

Based on these values, the 7 training needs with the highest value were selected, also ensuring a good balance between training on soft and hard skills:

- **SOFT SKILLS**
 - People management
 - Service orientation
 - Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration
- **HARD SKILLS**
 - Digital skills
 - Project management
 - Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies etc
 - EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization, with a focus on hemp

Taking into account the high request for project management training (6,14 as an average result), two modules (on different PM techniques) were dedicated to this topic.

After the discussion on duration and budget, the final training modules, topics of the call for training tender, are the following:

Training module	Maximum budget	Minimum training hours
Module 1 – Digital and analytical skills	7,000 €	12
Module 2 – PM ² methodology	8,500 €	16
Module 3 – Lean management	4,000 €	10
Module 4 – Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies, etc	2,500 €	6
Module 5 – EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization	2,000 €	5
Module 6 – Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration	3,000 €	7
Module 7 – Service orientation as a strategic marketing tool	3,000 €	7
Module 8 – People management	3,000 €	7

Table 5. Training modules: topic, budget and duration

The content of each training module is detailed in Annex A.

3.2 Publication of the call for training tender

The call for tender was published on 31st August 2022 on:

- Project website (<https://hempclubproject.com/news/call-for-training-for-the-experts-recruitment-for-cluster-management-capacity-and-skills-building/>)
- ECCP platform (<https://clustercollaboration.eu/community-news/call-training-experts-recruitment-cluster-management-capacity-and-skills>)
- Social media (<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6970740797046427649>)

The call will remain open until the 30th of September 2022. During this period, experts can send their application to the HempClub Partnership by completing a letter of interest, a technical proposal and a financial proposal. Submission must be made via email to hempclubeu@gmail.com. Details on the submission procedure are available in Annex 1.

Training activities will start on the 31st of October 2022 and end on 5th of May 2022.

Annex 1 – Call for training tender

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Hemp Club

**COMPETENT AND CONNECTED
CLUSTERS UNFOLD THE HEMP
INDUSTRY POTENTIAL FOR THE
EUROPEAN BIOECONOMY**

Grant Agreement No: 101037874

**TERM OF REFERENCE (TENDER)
EXPERTS RECRUITMENT FOR CLUSTER
MANAGEMENT CAPACITY AND SKILLS BUILDING**

PUBLICATION DATE: 31 AUGUST 2022

Reference	HempClub Training 2022
Subject	Experts Recruitment for cluster management capacity and skills building
Countries	Italy, Czech Republic, Romania, Portugal, Austria
Description of the assignment	Training programme for cluster management capacity and skills building (7 clusters, 14 managers)
Project	Competent And Connected Clusters Unfold The Hemp Industry Potential For The European Bioeconomy (GA: 101037874)
Period of Assignment	31 st October 2022 – 5 th May 2023
Maximum budget	€ 33,000
Open date	31 st August 2022
Deadline	30 th September 2022
How to submit the proposal	The Proposal must be submitted by email to hempclubeu@gmail.com within the open date and the deadline as described above. Applications received before or after these dates will be disregarded.

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1. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

The Competent and Connected Clusters Unfold the Hemp Industry Potential for the European Bioeconomy (HempCluB) project is an EU COSME project coordinated by Lombardy Green Chemistry Association bringing together **7 clusters and associations** operating in the primary hemp production, bioeconomy, mechatronics and green chemistry sectors from **Italy, Czech Republic, Romania, Austria and Portugal**. HempCluB project works to unlock the **potential of hemp** by creating EU value chains for biobased applications and new business opportunities for primary producers and chemical companies. With its unique chemical properties, environmental benefits, high yield and wide range of applications, hemp is a valuable crop for the bioeconomy, contributing to achieving climate neutrality, although still representing a niche crop in Europe. As a **European Strategic Cluster Partnership**, HempCluB promotes collaboration, synchronised strategies, and encourages innovative interregional investments to enhance cluster excellence.

Among the specific objectives of the actions, HempClub Partership aims to improve the **management skills** and performance of cluster managers through a specialised and multidisciplinary training course. After assessing the performance of clusters and the needs for new skills of the HempClub partners, 14 managers (two for each cluster) will take part into 8 training modules for a total of 70 hours of training with the objectives of:

1. Strengthening managerial skills functional to achieving the Cluster Excellence Label certification.
2. Uptaking transversal facilitating skills for promoting high quality services to their members.

For further information about the project, please visit: <https://hempclubproject.com/>

2. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPES OF THE ASSIGNMENT

The specific objectives that the trainings intend to achieve are:

- To improve the skills of the trainees in the areas that were identified by the partnership as important to foster cluster excellence to HEMPCLUB partners.
- To build the capacity of managers to better manage the cluster activities and to create new services of high added value for the cluster and its members, in different themes namely digitalisation, bio-economy and new hemp value chains.
- To provide managers with the knowledge and tools to promote intra-institution and inter-institution collaboration
- To draw recommendations for the future delivery of effective services to SMEs, the creation of dedicated Exchange opportunities (for cluster members or other organisations)
- To report on the training performed and the achieved level of learning.

Subcontracts will be awarded for the recruitment of qualified expert(s) for training activities and methodologies for clusters, who will deliver a training programme on 8 modules as described below, for a total of 70 hours of training. The content of the training is based on the strategical and specific needs of the 7 clusters as identified in task 1.1 of the HempClub project.

These training activities are addressed to the seven HempClub partners and will include at least two representatives from each organisation.

Training modules description

Module 1 – Digital and analytical skills: in this training module, cluster managers will learn about data analytics methodologies and visualization tools for KPI assessment and monitoring, usage of CRM programs to integrate data processing and management.

Module 2 – PM² methodology: in order to strengthen the cluster value proposition and deliver efficient solutions to their members, cluster managers will undertake a training course on the PM² methodology, the official project management methodology developed by the European Commission. Based on operational experience from projects run within the European Institutions and incorporating elements from a wide range of globally accepted project management best practices, standards and methodologies, the adoption of this methodology increases the effectiveness, efficiency and success of projects and programmes undertaken by public and private EU organizations.

Module 3 – Lean management: to improve efficiency and quality in the organisation management, cluster managers will learn about lean management, an approach that focuses on the concept of improvement of work processes, purpose and people.

Module 4 – Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies, etc: this training module will provide cluster managers with tools for facilitating bioeconomy and circular economy business models and to support matchmaking in bioeconomy and circular approaches and cross-sectoral opportunities.

Module 5 – EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization: this module will analyse the legislative and policy framework at EU level on bioeconomy and biomass valorization, with a focus on hemp. The aim of this training is to highlight positive framework for biomass and hemp valorization while identifying major limitations in EU policy. While the focus will be the European Union, a short introduction on major policies in partners countries will be carried out.

Module 6 – Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration: this module will provide to cluster managers tools and strategies to build and maintain collaborative teams with a focus on the organizational support. This soft skill will be crucial for cluster managers to foster effective collaboration and high-performing teamwork.

Module 7 – Service orientation as a strategic marketing tool: this training module provides cluster managers with tool to look for the best services for the clients and at the same time for services that are most profitable to the organisation. Learning the service management will help cluster to develop more and more competitive services that could strongly benefit their members.

Module 8 – People management: this training module will provide an introduction on performance management and the signs of a high performing team, setting performance objectives and managing conflicts. It will also provide cluster managers with tips on how to coach their team.

Each expert can send an offer related to one or more lots, according to their own area of knowledge and experience. The following table summarizes the maximum available budget for each lot and the minimum number of training hours.

Training module	Maximum budget	Minimum training hours
Module 1 – Digital and analytical skills	7,000 €	12
Module 2 – PM ² methodology	8,500 €	16
Module 3 – Lean management	4,000 €	10
Module 4 – Bioeconomy: strategies, technologies, etc	2,500 €	6
Module 5 – EU policy framework on bioeconomy and biomass valorization	2,000 €	5
Module 6 – Fostering teamwork and enabling others for collaboration	3,000 €	7
Module 7 – Service orientation as a strategic marketing tool	3,000 €	7
Module 8 – People management	3,000 €	7

This application is open to trainers/facilitators who are specialized in completing trainings/workshops and have proven and demonstrated broad knowledge of and ability to implement the principles, methods, techniques and systems of mentoring in relation to the above-described training topics.

3. REPORTS, DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The reports, duties and responsibilities of the expert(s) providing the training consist of, but are not limited to, the following:

- *The preparation of the contents and materials for the capacity building.* The training will include at least one of the seven core modules described in paragraph 2 and will be delivered by the expert(s). The details of the training programme will be sent to the participants at least two weeks before the date the training is scheduled to take place.
- *The expert(s) will deliver training in a dedicated location set by the consortium or virtually.* The place of the training will be defined on a case-by-case basis. For more information about the location of the training, see paragraph 6.
- *On completion of the training, the expert(s) will provide adequate follow-up material.* This include: i) the training material (including the presentations used); ii) a report on the training activities including the assessment of the achieved level by participants and a recommendation on how further develop and implement the training topic. All the reports are subject to the approval from the contractor to finalise the payment to the expert and shall be delivered electronically both in modifiable and non-modifiable format in clear quality English.

4. QUALIFICATION AND SKILLS OF THE TRAINER(S)

General application requirements

Applicants must meet the following general criteria:

- Applicants must have their permanent residence in a COSME country;
- Applicants must submit their application by email to hempclubeu@gmail.com within the open date (31st August 2022) and the deadline (30th September 2022). Applications received before or after these dates will be disregarded;
- Applications must be completed in all its parts (administrative, technical and financial part, see Annexes) and must be written in English;
- It is possible to apply for more than one training modules but it is not possible to send multiple applications.

Professional experience and qualifications:

- University degree in relevant field;
- Fully proficient in speaking, writing and understanding English;
- Advances university degree (i.e. Master or PhD) are considered an asset;
- A minimum of three (3) years of professional experience in training and building capacity;
- Previous experience with cluster management training is an asset;
- Previous training experience with organizations in the hemp and bioeconomy sectors is an asset.

Specific Experience and Qualifications:

- Excellent inter-personal communication skills including experience of facilitation of trainings/workshops and presentation.
- Proven and demonstrated broad knowledge of and ability to utilize principles, methods, techniques and systems of project management.
- Experience of delivering trainings for at least one of the 7 training modules according to HEMPCLUB modules is required. Examples of previous training are required.
- Experience with cluster analysis.

Applicants can be either organisations (companies, foundations, etc.) or natural persons.

5. TIMEFRAME OF THE ASSIGNMENT

The duration of the assignment will be of maximum seven months upon the signature of the contract.

TIMEFRAME OF THE ASSIGNMENT	
Expected start date of the assignment	31 st October 2022
Expected completion date of the assignment	5 th May 2023

This timeframe includes any preliminary activities for the preparation of the training contents and materials and the completion of the final report on the training activities. The assignment is considered completed after the contracting authority approves the final report on the training activities. The contractor will finalise the payment of the balance only after its formal approval of the service performed and the deliverables submitted.

Contractors have to establish a calendar scheduled for each training modules. The dates of each training module will be agreed between the expert(s) and the contracting authority based on the training calendar proposed by the contractor. The contractor will confirm the exact dates at the contract signature.

6. LOCATION

All the fourteen participants partners will receive the training together in the same location or at the same time, if remotely training. The location is expected to be agreed among the contractors and the contracting authorities. The training could be organized entirely face-to-face, remotely or in an hybrid form. The HempClub Partnership plans to organize 50% of the training modules face-to-face and the other 50% online.

Any costs related to the e-platform, in case of providing a virtual training, or related to travel, in case that the expert(s) providing a face-to-face training is required to change location, must be included in the financial offer as part of the lump sum (see Annex 3).

In case of unexpected events or force majeure, the coordinator reserves the right to change location of the training; should this be necessary, the new location will be communicated to the expert(s) no later than 15 days before the training scheduled date.

7. CONTRACTING AUTHORITY

HempClub is a partnership of 7 different clusters and associations from 5 different EU countries. However, only the coordinator will be responsible for contracting the recruited expert(s).

Thus, the contracting authority is:

LOMBARDY GREEN CHEMISTRY ASSOCIATION (LGCA), established in PIAZZA DELLA TRIVULZIANA 4/A, MILANO 20126, Italy, VAT number: IT09571440966.

8. REPORTING AND PAYMENT

An advance payment, equal to 40% of the contract amount, will be paid to the expert(s) upon signature of the contract and the remaining 60% will be paid within 30 days after the completion of the service. The payment of the balance, in the form of a lump sum, will be made upon approval of the reports submitted by the contractor.

The lump sum will include all costs incurred by the expert(s), including travel and accommodation if necessary, as detailed in the Financial Proposal (Annex 3).

Payments will be made in Euros. The amount paid to the expert(s) shall be gross and inclusive of all associated costs such as social security, income tax, VAT, travel costs and any other expenditure.

9. HOW TO APPLY

Applicants must submit the following applications documents via email to hempclubeu@gmail.com by stating “HempClub: proposal for the training programme for cluster management capacity and skills building” as the subject of the email, between 31st August 2022 and 30st September 2022.

All documents and information provided must be in English.

- A letter of interest (Annex 1) containing contact details of the expert and explaining why they, he/she is the most suitable for the work (max 1 page).
- Technical proposal (Annex 2) detailing the methodology and the content of the training. The application should also indicate a possible timing and location for the training (max 5 pages).
- Financial proposal (Annex 3) detailing all the costs incurred in preparing and providing the training, including the costs for the e-platform or for travelling. A breakdown of the lump sum per training modules, if applying for more than one training, is mandatory. The price for the tender must be

quoted in euro. Costs incurred by the candidate(s) in preparing and submitting the applications will not be reimbursed.

- CVs of the expert(s) involved in the training.

Only complete applications will be considered for selection/evaluation.

All annexes (excluding CVs) must be digitally signed.

10. EVALUATION OF APPLICATIONS

The applications will be evaluated by the **HempClub Evaluation Committee**, composed of 7 members (at least one representative for each partner). The evaluation process will consist of an initial evaluation, carried out individually by each member of the Evaluation Committee, and a subsequent panel assessment, where experts reach an agreement on the proposal evaluation.

The selected proposals must demonstrate high quality and excellent experience in training, cluster managements and on the specific training topic(s) for which the expert(s) apply. The evaluation process will take into account both the technical content and the financial proposal, contributing to the final score for 70% and 30%, respectively.

The selection of the expert(s) will be based on the general criterion of the best value for money for the delivery of the objectives. Qualifications and professional experience as well as previous experiences will be relevant for the evaluation.

After evaluating proposal eligibility based on the general criteria define in paragraph 4, each member of the Evaluation Committee will assign 20 points to each proposal, considering the following criteria:

- **General qualifications and professional qualifications and experience:** max 4 points
- **Technical proposal** (including the methodology and the content of the training): max 10 points
- **Price proposal:** max 6 points

Individual scores obtained for each member of the Evaluation Committee will be cumulated.

Total max score per applicant: 140 points.

Only proposal reaching the threshold of 84 points or more will be considered for the assignment. A ranking of successful proposals will be established and the proposals with the highest score will be awarded.

Annex 1 – Letter of interest

CONTACT INFORMATION	
Name of the organization or Person	
Contact Person	
Address	
VAT number	
E-mail	
Telephone	
Website	

SUMMARY OF THE PROPOSAL	
Training module(s)	
Financial offer (total amount)	
Total hour of training	
Previous experience in the field	<i>Max 400 characters (space included) per each module</i>

HOW THE PROFILE OF THE APPLICANTS IS ALIGNED WITH THE HEMPCLUB REQUESTS
<i>Max 600 characters (space included)</i>

Annex 2 – Technical proposal

Organization and experience

Describe the organization, with a focus on your knowledge, skills and experience in the field. Please, include concrete examples of past work related to the assignment.

Approach and Methodology

Describe your approach and methodology for training, including the implementation of actions to achieve the goals described in paragraph 2. Include, whenever possible, specific reference on how the proposed training could benefit cluster managers and their members.

Work Plan

Describe in detail the content of the proposed training and its timing.

Team composition

For each team member, provide a short CV (no more than 15 rows) and describe how his/her/their competences are suitable to the assigned task(s). Moreover, complete the following summary table.

Name	Area(s) of expertise	Assigned task(s)

Annex 3 – Financial proposal

TRAINING MODULE N. XX	
Description of the expenses	Amount (€)
Personel costs for XX hours of work (including hours of training and preparatory work)	
Cost for teaching material	
Travel expenses for XX (please, define how many people travelling and for how many days if needed)	
E-platform for virtual teaching (if needed)	
Other: please, specify	
TOTAL	

Copy the above table for every training module you are applying for.